

Sulphur Elimination from Copper Pyrite by Methanol

V. P. GUPTA*^a and SUDHIR DANEJ^b

^aDepartment of Science, Regional College of Education (NCERT), Bhopal-462 013

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Govt. Polytechnic, Ujjain-456 010

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In India, we have large deposits of iron pyrite at Amjhore (Bihar) and of copper pyrite at Malanjkh- and (Madhya Pradesh) and Khetri (Rajasthan). These deposits of iron and copper have been exploited for the recovery of sulphur and metals by thermal decomposition and other methods^{1,2}. These large deposits of sulphide ores may also be utilised for the recovery of elemental sulphur and for the preparation of different organosulphur compounds by treating them with alcohols. No systematic study has been reported in the literature on the reaction of metal sulphides with organic compounds except that reported on the reaction of iron pyrite with methanol³ and ethanol⁴ wherein respectively 57.70 and 54.50% sulphur could be eliminated. These two studies opened a new dimension in the direction of exploitation of sulphide ores in our country for the recovery of elemental sulphur and preparation of organosulphur compounds.

This study of the reaction of methanol with natural copper pyrite obtained from Hindustan Copper Project, Malanjkh- and was conducted to see the extent to which the sulphur can be eliminated at low temperatures. Another objective of the study was to develop a single non-catalytic method for the preparation of organosulphur compounds like mercaptans and sulphides. Development of alternative, metallurgical methods for the recovery of metals from the easily digestible metal sulphides present in the residue left after the reaction was another objective of this study. Hence, in the present study, an attempt has been made to develop a process for the maximum elimination of sulphur from natural copper pyrite by studying the effect of different process variables like particle size, flow rate, space velocity, temperature, reaction period and partial pressure of methanol.

Results and Discussion

The gaseous effluent was found to be H₂S and estimated by standard chemical method⁵. CH₃SH and CH₃SCH₃⁶ were found to be present in the liquid effluent as confirmed by chemical and spectroscopic methods.

The effect of various process variables on sulphur elimination from copper pyrite is discussed below. The effects of particle size, flow rate and space velocity were studied at 450° for reaction period of 30 min. Sulphur elimination increased from 4.58 to 10.90% on decreasing the particle size from -60+85 to -100+120 B.S. mesh. However, beyond the particle size of -100+120 B.S. mesh

sulphur elimination started decreasing though to a small extent, perhaps due to the compactness of the pyrite bed. The effect of flow rate study indicates that sulphur elimination increases from 9.92 to 13.53% on increasing the flow rate from 9.43 to 36.43 dm³ h⁻¹. When the reaction was performed with the flow rate of 46.07 dm³ h⁻¹, sulphur elimination decreased to 9.72% which could be due to the fact that on increasing the flow rate of methanol, contact time between alcohol vapour and pyrite bed decreased to such a great extent beyond 36.63 dm³ h⁻¹ that sulphur elimination decreased. For studying the effect of space velocity, volume of pyrite bed was kept as 1 ml for getting space velocity upto 4.607 × 10⁴ ml ml⁻¹ h⁻¹. For studying the effect of space velocities, the bed volume was reduced to 0.5 ml to increase the contact time. It was found that initially sulphur elimination increases from 5.18 to 13.53% with increase in space velocity from 9.43 × 10³ to 3.6 × 10⁴ ml ml⁻¹ h⁻¹. This was perhaps due to the easy release of gaseous or low boiling products from the reaction sphere due to the high flow rate of methanol vapour. The similar trend has been reported by early workers in the reaction of iron pyrite with steam², methanol³, ethanol⁴ and oxidation of iron pyrite in a fixed bed⁷. Beyond space velocity of 3.6 × 10⁴ ml ml⁻¹ h⁻¹ the sulphur elimination becomes almost constant.

The effect of temperature has been studied in the temperature range 400–650° for reaction period of 30 min, and the results are graphically represented in Fig. 1. The shape of the graph shows that sulphur elimination increases on raising the temperature. At 400°, only 7.12% sulphur could be recovered which increased to 18.57% at 550° and 19.69% at 575°. On increasing the temperature from 575 to 600° sulphur elimination further increased to 28.26%. On increasing the temperature from 600 to 650° not much change in sulphur elimination was observed.

The effect of reaction period was studied at 550° and 600° and the results are presented in Fig. 2. The reaction period varied from 2 min to 3 h. At 550° in 2 min, only 8.12% sulphur could be eliminated which rose to 13.00% in 5 min and 15.40% in 10 min. Very little change was observed in the rate of sulphur elimination from 15 to 30 min when 18.57% sulphur was recovered. Maximum sulphur elimination took place in 150 min when 40.59% sulphur was removed. During this reaction, the percent of H₂S elimination rose from 6.01 to 13.75% whereas the percent of organosulphur compounds increased from 2.11 to 26.84% on increasing the

Fig. 1. Effect of temperature.

Fig. 2. Effect of reaction period at various temperatures: (O) 550° and (Δ) 600°.

reaction period from 2 to 150 min. Almost the same trend was observed at 600° when the sulphur elimination increased from 9.40% in 2 min to 34.96% in 120 min. Higher reaction periods beyond 120 min were not studied at 600° as a very little change of 2.87% was found in sulphur elimination on increasing the temperature from 550 to 600°.

The effect of partial pressure of methanol was investigated at 550° using three partial pressures of 0.3, 0.5 and 1 atm. For partial pressures of 0.3 and 0.5 atm, pure and dry nitrogen gas was also passed along with alcohol vapours. All other process variables were kept constant like the other runs. As is evident from Fig. 3, very little change in sulphur elimination took place by changing the

Fig. 3. Effect of reaction period at different partial pressures: (O) 0.3, (Δ) 0.5 and (□) 1.5 atm.

partial pressure from 0.3 to 0.5 atm. Sulphur elimination increased from 20.40 to 21.69% in 60 min on changing the partial pressure of methanol vapours from 0.3 to 0.5 atm. By keeping the partial pressure at 1 atm, 24.40% sulphur could be eliminated under the same set of conditions. A maximum amount of 40.59% sulphur could be eliminated in 150 min at 1 atm in comparison to 36.01% at 0.5 atm.

Optimum conditions: The optimum conditions for maximum elimination of sulphur are as follows: particle size, -100+120 mesh; flow rate, 36.63 dm³ h⁻¹; space velocity, 3.663 × 10⁴ ml ml⁻¹ h⁻¹; temperature, 550°; reaction period, 150 min; partial pressure of CH₃OH, 1 atm. Under these conditions 40.59% sulphur could be eliminated, 13.75% was in the form of H₂S and 26.84% in the form of organo-

sulphur compounds. CH_3SH and CH_3SCH_3 could be confirmed by chemical tests, ir spectra and gas chromatography. The results are reproducible within a range of 0.2%. Material balance has been found 99.80% in term of Cu and 99.84% in term of Fe.

Conclusion: In this reaction of methanol and copper pyrite, only 40.59% sulphur could be eliminated at 550° in 150 min in comparison to 57.70% in the interaction of iron pyrite with methanol³ at the same temperature. This low elimination of sulphur can be attributed to the strong bonding of sulphur with copper and iron in copper pyrite. This is further supported by the fact that during the reaction of methanol with iron pyrite it took only 15 min for 57.70% sulphur elimination, whereas in case of copper pyrite it took 150 min for 40.59% sulphur elimination.

For getting maximum sulphur elimination, 162 ml of methanol was passed for 150 min over a pyrite bed of 1 ml volume weighing about 2 g, i.e. about 4 moles of methanol was required for getting 13.75% of sulphur as H_2S and 26.84% of sulphur in different organosulphur compounds. Most of the methanol was present as such in the effluents which can be recovered and recycled. Elemental sulphur can be recovered from H_2S by the traditional methods. This reaction has also resulted in the single-step non-catalytic method for the preparation of different organosulphur compounds from the vast deposits of copper pyrite in our country. The solid residue left after the run contains major portion of easily digestible sulphides and oxides of iron and copper from which these metals can be easily recovered at comparatively lower temperatures.

Experimental

The natural copper pyrite ore was supplied by Hindustan Copper Limited, Copper Project, Malanjkhand, Balaghat District situated in the state of Madhya Pradesh which contained 2.5–4.0% of copper pyrite in open cast mine. This material was crushed for size reduction and froth-flotation technique was used for concentration. The concentrated sample was black in colour and appeared like mud having a metallic lustre. X-ray diffraction data confirmed CuFeS_2 as the major component, FeS_2 in good amount, SiO_2 in remarkable amount and oxides and sulphides of iron and copper in minor amount. The sample was given washings with hot water to remove soluble sulphates. The sample was dried and screened through different sieves to get samples of different particle sizes. The composition of samples of different particle sizes is given in Table 1.

Solid residue left after the reaction was weighed and treated with hot water to estimate water-soluble sulphates etc. if any, formed during the reaction. The residue-A left after hot water treatment was

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF SAMPLES OF NATURAL COPPER PYRITE

Sl. no.	Particle size (B.S. mesh)	Analysis %				
		Cu	Fe	S	SiO_2	O as oxides
1.	-60+85	23.30	31.14	34.13	9.32	2.12
2.	-85+100	25.22	30.50	33.20	9.16	1.92
3.	-100+120	26.00	29.69	33.73	9.26	1.32
4.	-120+150	26.80	30.80	32.82	8.95	0.62
5.	-150+170	26.79	29.89	32.80	9.27	1.24

digested with 1:1 HCl to calculate the soluble sulphides and oxides of iron and copper. The residue-B left after digestion was brominated by the standard method⁶ to assess the unreacted CuFeS_2 and FeS_2 . The residue-C left after bromination was heated to 1000° to determine the insoluble silica. Iron, copper and sulphur present in the residue left after the reaction were estimated by the standard methods⁵. Solid products analysed by the above chemical methods were also confirmed by X-ray diffraction.

The reaction of copper pyrite with methanol was studied in a fixed-bed tubular glass reactor in the temperature range $400-650^\circ$ by following the procedure reported earlier.

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